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Dissemination & Communication Plan

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DEL	Technical reports identified as deliverables in the Description of Work	X
MoM	Minutes of Meeting	
MAN	Procedures and user manuals	
WOR	Working document, issued as preparatory documents to a technical report	
INF	Information and Notes	

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PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
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Acronyms and Abbreviations

PROJECT BENEFICIARIES:

JSI: Jožef Stefan Institute, Slovenia
IPMA: Instituto Portugues do Mar e da Atmosfera, Portugal
UNIBO: Alma Mater Studiorum Universita di Bologna, Italy
Eurofish: Eurofish International Organization, Denmark
UNIFI: Universita degli Studi di Firenze, Italy
UMF: University of Medicine and Pharmacy, "Iuliu Hațieganu" Cluj-Napoca, Romania
DTU: Danmarks Tekniske Universitet, Denmark
BTU: Brandenburg University of Technology Cottbus-Senftenberg, Germany
NORCE: Norwegian Research Centre, Norway
EuroFIR: European Food Information Resources, Belgium
UNIPD: University of Padova, Italy
ABT: AquaBio Tech, Malta
REDINN: RETE EUROPEA DELL'INNOVAZIONE, Italy
BELIT: Preduzece za informacione tehnologije I elektronsko trgovanje BELIT DOO, Serbia
MICRUX: MICRUX FLUIDIC SL, Spain
JdIC: DE LA CUEVA GONZALEZ COTERA JAVIER, Spain
CETGA: Centro Tecnológico del Cluster de la Acuicultura, Spain
DigitalSmart: DigitalSmart DOO, Monte Negro
Bugenvila: BUGENVILA INVESTICIJE DOO, Croatia
OXY: Oxyguard, Denmark

ASSOCIATED PARTNER ORGANISATIONS:

WRG: WRG Europe Ltd, United Kingdom
EAS: EU Aquaculture Society, Belgium

ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS:

CA: Consortium Agreement
CLLs: Co-creation Living Labs
EATIP: European Aquaculture Technology and Innovation Platform
EB: Executive Board
EC: European Commission
EEAB: External Expert Advisory Board
EFSA: European Food Safety Agency
EIT: European Institute of Technology Food
ENOLL: European Networks of Living Labs
GA Grant Agreement
PC: Project Coordinator
USG: User Stakeholder Group
WP: Work Package

Executive Summary

This document is a revised version of Deliverable 8.1; the Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation (CD&E) plan for FishEUTrust. It describes the activities and timings to maximise exploitation and impact of the primary project outcomes through effective communications (creation of general information about the project to target audiences) and dissemination (disclosure of specific project results to potentially interested parties to support commercial and non-commercial (e.g. academic) exploitation).

Communication and dissemination activities include creation of a project website, infographics, videos (animations, motion graphics, and film), social media posting, project newsletters, conferences, scientific and trade publications, and events (including open days).

The project CD&E activities are closely linked to other related work packages/tasks such as consumer engagement/interventions (WP2), business models (WP3), clustering with other similar projects (WP8), and digital platforms (WP7). As these Work Packages progress, they will increasingly feed into and optimise the CD&E plan. Consequently, this is a live document that will be updated throughout the life of the project, with the final version being delivered at Month 48.

1. Introduction

Increased urbanisation and retail development have significantly modified dietary behaviours and disrupted long-established ecological, agricultural, cultural and economic norms. Moreover, consumption and seafood exports have decreased due to increased fish prices, reduced consumer uptake, market access and logistical problems caused by transportation and border restrictions. Meeting the FOOD 2030 challenges in the context of global food scenarios (food demand will increase by approximately 60 % by 2050 according to FAO) will require innovative measures that deliver sustainable, resilient, responsible, competitive and inclusive food systems within the frame of a circular bioeconomy while providing a healthy diet and engaging EU communities.

Ensuring the safety, quality, and authenticity of fish and seafood has never been more complex than it is today, and it will be increasingly challenging in the future. Although the quality of fish and seafood products is generally high in Europe, product traceability and microbiological safety methods are limited and need to be improved to increase consumer confidence and thus uptake.

The Eurobarometer of EU consumer habits regarding the fishery and aquaculture products reveals that a product origin is the third most mentioned factor in purchasing decisions after cost¹. The EU is also the world's largest importer of fish (24% of the total value of world fish trade), and consumers are generally faced with fish and shellfish of little-known origin with little information about fishing, e.g. gear, feed, welfare issues, processing and transport details, which adds to existing lack of trust, especially regarding farmed seafood. Further, EU consumers are also keen to have additional information about the fish and seafood they buy (e.g. date of catch/harvest, condition of growing). The growing demand by consumers for environmental information, and to a lesser degree ethical and social information, confirms the need to adopt a farm-to-fork strategy that empowers consumers to access sustainable products. Reversing the current trends of declining fish consumption by promoting a higher fish and seafood content in diets, with associated nutritional benefits and low ecological and carbon footprints, will require original thinking, which is the primary overarching aim of FishEUTrust and will be achieved through the project specific objectives.

A comprehensive Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation (CD&E) plan is fundamental to ensuring optimal and timely impact of FishEUTrust and subsequent exploitation of outcomes. FishEUTrust is a complex project with several interrelated CD&E activities that will evolve and develop over time (e.g. clustering, consumer engagement, business models, etc.). For the purposes of this deliverable, at this early stage, this document is an outline of the intentions for CD&E and the anticipated routes that will be taken to maximise impact. This plan is a living document and will be updated and amended as new information and data are acquired, with a final report on CD&E activities delivered at the end of the project. CD&E effectiveness will be monitored regularly (see section 6), and additional measures added as required.

¹ <https://europa.eu/eurobarometer/surveys/detail/2271>

1.1 Definition of Communication versus Dissemination

In order for the distinction between communication and dissemination to be clear throughout this document, the following “definitions” are used:

Communication

Communication is a one or two-way dialogue with your target audience(s) and beyond with the aim to reach out to society as a whole and, in particular, to some specific audiences while demonstrating how EU funding contributes to tackling societal challenges.

Dissemination

Dissemination is the public disclosure of the results to audiences that may be interested in using them. This means that you transfer the knowledge and results that you have produced (with appropriate protection such as patents) to those that can best make use of it (e.g. research peers, industry, other commercial actors, professional organisations, policymakers, etc.).

2. Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan

Work Package 8 (WP8) covers the primary FishEUTrust communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities, but is strongly interrelated to other work packages, such as WP2 (consumer intervention strategies and engagement) and WP3 (business cases).

WP8 specific objectives are as follows:

- 08.1:** To manage and integrate all related WP activities relating to engagement and outreach in order to create and maintain a comprehensive dissemination and communication plan.
- 08.2:** To develop a project brand identity and to create and maintain a dedicated and integrated website/portal to highlight results and provide general informational material and data.
- 08.3:** To produce and facilitate high quality general communication materials, scientific/trade publications, and events to disseminate the results of the project to target audiences.
- 08.4:** To implement a supply-chain engagement campaign (from farm-to-fork) to maximise awareness and exploitation of the project technologies and approaches by key stakeholders, including support from policymakers.
- 08.5:** Develop clustering and synergies with existing dissemination channels and networks to raise awareness about the project's results and foster collaboration and exploitation through other EU initiatives.

The FishEUTrust CD&E plan, developed and refined via on-going activities within WPs 2, 3, and 8, will ensure that:

1. Project outputs and innovations are converted into commercial opportunity, competitively consolidating and growing existing markets, as well as non-commercial exploitation such as new academic collaborative research ventures.
2. All project outputs will be actively disseminated and promoted among stakeholders and interested parties inside and outside the consortium through a comprehensive business plan and exploitation programme.

These measures will create the desired socio-economic impacts including public health, EU market growth, and environmental sustainability.

The CD&E plan has been tailored to generate maximum awareness of the project outcomes, amongst consumers, industrial parties (fish industry and retail), investors, governmental and regulatory bodies, and potential customers in addition to academics and research organisations.

2.1 Parties responsible for communication, dissemination, and exploitation

WP8 is led by WRG Europe (UK). However, this WP is also strongly dependent on input from all beneficiaries, but particularly from Norce (supply-chain, stakeholder, and industrial engagement), EuroFish (networking and creating synergies with existing projects and initiatives), and EuroFIR (best practices and networking and engagement with the food industry in general).

WP8 leader, Mark Langley (WRG), is the Dissemination and Exploitation Officer on the General Assembly (GA) and will receive input and support from relevant project organisations. The GA will oversee the CD&E strategy for the project, coordinate activities, and liaise with beneficiaries about protection (intellectual property) and exploitation of outcomes, both commercial and non-commercial. Moreover, the management has been structured to allow input into CD&E activities from both data management and innovation and exploitation management teams (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Management structure to support CD&E measures

2.2 Target groups and audiences

The aims, key results, and important outcomes of FishEUTrust will be communicated and disseminated freely and globally (after IP protection when required), and will inform target audiences of the scientific, economic, and social value of FishEUTrust.

The following target audiences have been identified:

- The public to inform them, in general, of EU seafood supply, aquaculture, and current practices.
- Consumers across the EU need to be engaged to understand their purchasing preferences and important factors that influence their choices. This understanding derives from consumer intervention strategies (WP2) that seek to encourage informed purchasing of fish and seafood from high-quality EU sources.
- Industrial stakeholders (large industry and SMEs) interested in adopting project developments (production or retail) to assure seafood quality, authenticity, and safety.
- Research community, with a particular focus on: (a) research in food science disciplines interested in developing and implementing advanced sensors, genomics, and tools to determine and monitor product authenticity, safety, and quality; and (b) social scientists interested in consumer behaviour and requirements.
- Policymakers and food control agencies who will benefit from FishEUTrust technology activities, particularly those related to seafood quality, safety, and standards.

Different types of media creation will be used for different target audiences as shown in Table 1. While the Target Groups as shown generically in this Table, detail on Target Groups is given in Section 3.

Type	Target Groups	Tools	Type of Engagement
Project media creation and distribution	Industry and SME. Researchers. Policy and Legal bodies. Consumers.	Project Corporate Identity: Logo and identity, MS Office templates used as a common public identity for all management, communication and dissemination activities. The project logo will be implemented on a media.	Material: Project leaflets, factsheets, promotional flyers for target stakeholders, additional promotional flyers for open events, scientific posters, promo roll-up, brochure on final results.
Digital media and platforms	Industry and SME. Researchers. Policy and Inspector bodies. Consumers.	A public website integrated with FishEUTrust activities, including data access, user logins, user experience surveys, informative content, news & events, e-learning tools & materials, video animations, integrated social media accounts. The project will map appropriate communication channels, individuals and organisations, user communities to include in the FishEUTrust network.	Material: Digital and awareness campaigns, events and activated networks to help redirect to the website where data and services can be accessed. Regular social media activity will also help to generate followers.
Scientific and technical	Researchers. Industry and SME.	Scientific papers will be published to inform scientific communities and potential users about FishEUTrust achievements. Publications will be through high-ranking, peer-reviewed multidisciplinary journals and more specialised peer-reviewed international journals. Technical papers and application specific results will be published in trade journals and media, targeting end user groups. All publications will be available via open access channels. Gold open access will be the default standard unless data and/or IP prevents this. In any case publications will be made available via public online repositories and the projects webpage.	Material: social media campaigns alerting target groups to new publications; lay summaries for industry and SMEs highlighting new outputs.
Conferences, Workshops, Trade fairs, Symposia	Industry & SME; Researchers, Policy & Legal bodies, Consumers	The consortium will define important international conferences to be attended by its members to present the latest achievements, to discuss progress, developments and challenges in this field, and to find new industrial partners.	Events: Aquaculture Europe, Eurosensors, IEEE Sensors Conference, and for Food technology EFFoST International Conference. Also, to reduce travel costs the consortium plans to organise, where possible, consortium meetings in conjunction with these conferences (such as EuroFIR Food Forum) Material: Project leaflets, factsheets, promotional flyers, scientific posters,

			promo roll-up, brochure on final results.
Press and Media	Industry, SME, Researchers, Consumers	Press releases will be made at relevant points in the project such as interim results and key achievement, or for activities and events. Additionally, press and media representative will be invited to the final project PR event.	Material: press releases (EN), press releases translated by beneficiaries

Table 1: Target groups and engagement methods for FishEUTrust

2.3 Maximising Reach Through Partner Networks and Clustering

The project's outreach capacity is maximised through the inclusion of critical partners with a wide network of contacts in related public circles, industry and academia. For example, Eurofish currently has a network of over 1000 members in more than 60 countries across the world, as well as engagement with relevant associations. As an international organization, Eurofish will utilise its global network through Globefish to communicate results on a global scale. Eurofish also publishes the Eurofish Magazine in Europe to reach targeted audiences through articles (see also Section 3.5).

EuroFIR (European Food Information Resources) is an association set up to ensure advocacy of food information and to develop, publish and exploit international collaboration and standards to improve the quality of food information as well as access and re-use. It has more than 60 Members from globally who have interest in food-related research, data, policy, and standards as well as a network of more than 2000 organisations and individuals with an interest in food information.

There is a clustering activity within WP8 that will bring together not just relevant networks, but also related projects (EU-funded or otherwise) for mutual benefit and achievement of outcomes. For example, Table 2 below shows a short segment from a table within the current Clustering Plan (Deliverable 8.5) that shows the wide range of projects, networks, and organisations with which FishEUTrust could potentially collaborate.

ALLIANCE	A holistic framework in the quality labelled food supply chain systems' management towards enhanced data Integrity and veracity, interoperability, transparency, and traceability
AQUAINVERT	Development of sustainable, integrated and innovative aquaculture in Macaronesia: research and development to promote the production of marine invertebrates of commercial interest
ARCTAQUA	Cross-Border innovations in Arctic Aquaculture
ARGOS	Shared Governance of Sustainable fisheries and aquaculture activities as leverage to protect marine resources in the Adriatic Sea
ARIEL Plus	Promoting small scale fisheries and aquaculture transnational networking in Adriatic-Ionian macroregion
ASTRAL	All Atlantic Ocean Sustainable, Profitable and Resilient Aquaculture
Bivalvi	Advancing Europe an bivalve production systems
BLUEfasma	Empowering innovation capacity of SMEs, maritime clusters and networks in MED islands and coastal areas to support blue circular economy growth in fishing/aquaculture
BRIDGE-BS	Advancing Black Sea Research and Innovation to Co-Develop Blue Growth within Resilient Ecosystems
CEDISAR	Coanálisis EDNA-QPCR para detección rápida de índice sanitario en rodaballo
CELAVIE	CELAVIE
CHORIZO	Changing practices and Habits through Open, Responsible, and social Innovation towards Zero food waste
COMFOCUS	Exploring Food Consumer Science on a European scale
Data4Food2030	Pathways towards a fair, inclusive and innovative Data Economy for Sustainable Food Systems
DEMETER	Building an Interoperable, Data-Driven, Innovative and Sustainable European Agri-Food Sector
DisruptAqua	Disruptive Technologies in the Arctic Seafood Sector
ENFASYS	Encouraging farmers towards sustainable farming systems through policy and business strategies

Table 2: A sample of potential projects and networks for clustering (from Deliverable D8.5)

As a specific example, FishEUTrust is in discussions with the Sea2See project (blockchain technology to boost visibility of sustainable seafood) about mutually beneficial activities to boost reach and outcomes. The clustering activities will continue throughout the project to multiply the reach of the project.

2.4 Horizon Results Platform and Horizon Results Booster

Another key pipeline to support dissemination and exploitation is the Horizon Results Platform, which is available through the EC Portal. As the project progresses, the consortium will identify Key Exploitable Results (KERs) which can be uploaded to the HRP. These will then be accessible to other projects, researchers, investors, policymakers, etc., who might be interested in using the results for collaborative or commercial purposes. Moreover, the project will also apply for the Horizon Results Booster services available from the European Commission to help support communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities.

2.5 Strategy for Exploitation

Successful demonstration of FishEUTrust technologies at the appropriate scale (i.e. by use of the Co-creation Living Labs -CLLs) will ensure that after project completion these can be taken forward into pre-commercial or fully commercial opportunities, including the necessary pathways for investment.

As part of the overall knowledge transfer activities, engagement and outreach programmes, extensive collaboration of all beneficiaries with end-users and stakeholders will take place (e.g. aquaculture farms, seafood producers, business-to-business, and the supply chain). WP1 (CLLs) and WP3 (Business Models) will directly validate the technical and economic performance at each level. Similarly, WP1 and WP3 will validate the technologies against standards and regulations as a platform enabling future market uptake.

Beneficiaries within the Management Team (see Figure 1) comprise leading organisations that also operate worldwide to support the identification of market applications and opportunities, where the FishEUTrust technologies and processes can be most effective. These include systems promoting aquaculture development worldwide in cooperation with respective seafood associations, and scientific and regulatory bodies as well as individuals.

Identification of market applications and opportunities will be just one component of the exploitation and business strategy as an integral part of the wider programme to encourage uptake and implementation of FishEUTrust concepts throughout Europe and globally. Targeted aquaculture/seafood sectors will be sea bream and mussels initially, but many of the technologies can be exploited for other fish and seafood species and food sectors.

CLLs will act as demonstrators for the industrial sectors. Perceived risk is one of the biggest barriers to commercial and industrial investment. However, by illustrating successful deployment of these technologies as exemplars supported by comprehensive performance analysis and cost/benefit breakdown within the developed business plans, end-users and stakeholders will obtain the primary information required to consider uptake and implementation in their sectors.

Engagement with end-users will run throughout the project, such that targeted uptakes will be in place within 6 to 12 months of the project end. The business plan outline will be further developed and consolidated during the project (WP3) and is structured around three stages (see Section 5 for details), building directly from the necessary multidisciplinary and cross sector beneficiaries in the consortium. This will be reinforced by extensive sector expertise and network capability within the Management Team (i.e., Eurofish, EuroFIR, and NORCE).

2.6 Outputs and timeline of activities

Table 3 below shows the deliverables for WP8, which represent important control points for CD&E activities. These deliverables are marked on the Gantt chart in Annex I, which shows all activities associated with FishEUTrust communication, dissemination, exploitation, and outreach. These control points will be used to review and revise CD&E activities to best align with project developments.

ID	Details	Responsible	Month
D8.1	Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan - PART 1	WRG	6
D8.2	Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan - PART 2	WRG	6
D8.3	Established sustainable comprehensive communication, dissemination and exploitation framework across all stakeholders and actors	WRG	48
D8.4	Project website	WRG	3
D8.5	Draft clustering plan	EuroFish	3
D8.6	Comprehensive supply-chain and stakeholder engagement framework	Norce	48

Table 3: FishEUTrust WP8 deliverables

2.7 Sex and Gender Aspects

The project will pay close attention to sex and gender aspects with respect to communication and dissemination. For example, gender balance of target audiences will be assessed, gender aspects with respect to surveys and responses will be taken into account, and use of language in communications will be reviewed prior to release. Further details of Sex and Gender policies for the project can be found in Deliverable 9.3 "Gender Aspect Plan".

3. Communication

FishEUTrust's strategy to communicate the activities and outputs to the various target groups will follow *Communicating EU research and innovation guidance*. Engaging with the public and industry is at the heart of FishEUTrust's communication strategy. It is, therefore, important that the project creates a strong identity that stakeholders can recognise and trust as well as CD&E activities that are implemented regularly to maintain awareness and interest.

3.1 FishEUTrust branding

At the outset of the project, FishEUTrust branding was conceptualised by a graphic designer working for WRG Europe. A colour palette was put together and complementary fonts selected. Several versions of the logo were presented at the kick-off meeting, including suggestions from beneficiaries and the favourite was chosen by majority vote (Figure 2).

This logo will appear on all FishEUTrust documentation, social media, webpages, and promotional material. In addition to the FishEUTrust logo, the colour palette will be used across all dissemination and communication material (see also Figure 2). All media will contain the necessary acknowledgement/declaration of EU-funding and disclaimers relating to authors' views.

Figure 2: FishEUTrust logo (colour and monochrome) and brand colour palette

3.1.1 FishEUTrust templates

A set of templates for FishEUTrust documentation (reports, minutes, etc.) has been developed using the colour palette above and circulated to the beneficiaries. As stated above, the templates carry the FishEUTrust logo, EU flag, and wording acknowledging EU-funding and disclaimers. Deliverables, reports, and other documentation will also use these templates (Figure 3).

Figure 3: FishEUTrust Word templates

A PowerPoint template has been produced for FishEUTrust presentations (Figure 4) including internal meetings, training events, and conferences. A range of slide designs has been created in “slide master” for different presentation scenarios (images, bullet point lists, etc.) The slides use the FishEUTrust colour scheme and include project and EU branding and acknowledgements (see Figure 4).

Figure 4: Various slides from the FishEUTrust PowerPoint template

3.2 Website

A dedicated FishEUTrust website (Figure 5) has been designed and built by WRG (see <https://www.fisheustrust.eu/>). The website will be managed by WRG throughout the duration of FishEUTrust (and for 2 years after the completion of the project), with regular updates on progress in the form of news items, articles (or blogs), information on events, updates from related projects and initiatives, and an annual newsletter.

The website adheres to the FishEUTrust colour scheme and makes full use of all branding. It was released for the beneficiaries to review and was subsequently modified based on feedback.

Figure 5: FishEUTrust website homepage

The website is the primary means by which industrial organisations, the scientific community, policymakers, and consumers/public can find out about the work being undertaken by the consortium.

As the project develops, the website will link to websites of other related projects and networks (e.g., Sea2See), fostering relationships to the mutual benefit of these projects or networks. The website will also share posts and links for relevant articles and events from related projects to support wider understanding of the research and commercial landscapes within which FishEUTrust is functioning.

The website will act as a repository for documents and articles for both private FishEUTrust members only (i.e. via NextCloud logins) and public (non-sensitive) consumption. Printable promotional material for use at conferences and events (e.g., flyers, posters, brochures) will be available for download.

As the project progresses, the website will be linked to the various data platforms and blockchain being developed within WP7. At the simplest level, this will be a simple URL link, but the website will be more integrated in the longer-term to allow data to be pushed from/to these platforms by user communities.

The website also contains a sign-up area for the FishEUTrust newsletter (and this will be enhanced to include mailshots for important updates).

Figure 6: FishEUTrust website sign-up

3.3 Social media

Social media is an important tool for communicating project updates, results, news, and events. LinkedIn, Twitter/X, and YouTube accounts have been created for FishEUTrust. They will be managed by WRG Europe who will regularly invite contributions from the consortium. WRG Europe will also encourage partners to follow and reshare the posts from their accounts to facilitate a wider reach of interested beneficiaries. A social media strategy has been developed by WRG Europe to ensure regular, meaningful, and targeted posts. This includes a series of Key Messages to defined audiences, appropriate hashtags, themes, and timing of posts (including alignment to International Days, e.g. as defined by the United Nations).

3.3.1 LinkedIn

At the beginning of the project, WRG set up a FishEUTrust LinkedIn account (Figure 7). Posts on LinkedIn are aimed mainly at professional organisations (i.e., academia and industry), focussing on events, results, and exploitable outputs. It is also an important platform to connect with related projects and networks that can help increase reach and impressions of posts. For example, connecting with sister project Sea2See will ensure a greater volume and variety of posts through resharing, as well as raising awareness across a broader range of events and topics.

Figure 7: FishEUTrust LinkedIn and Twitter home pages.

3.3.2 Twitter/X

A dedicated Twitter/X account has been set up at the start of the project and is managed by WRG Europe (Figure 7). While Twitter/X is also good for reaching academic and industrial organisations, it is more appropriate for public outreach and (limited) engagement (compared to LinkedIn). The account will connect with all relevant European Commission Twitter/X accounts who typically have a wider follower base. Appropriate Key Messages, hashtags and, potentially, use of promoted posts will help reach wider and targeted audiences.

3.3.3 YouTube

YouTube is an excellent platform to share longer-form visual content from the project, such as videos, recorded presentations, and vlogs. A YouTube account is available for FishEUTrust, and will become particularly important towards the latter stages of the project where filming of open day events at the CLLs and documentary style videos will be created, as well as long-form infographics, and demonstration videos of project technologies (see also 3.4.3).

3.4 Other e-resources

3.4.1 Newsletters

A project newsletter will be published bi-annually. This will provide information about the project status, updates on results, exploitable outcomes that can be shared openly, as well as educational material (e.g. on farmed fish). The newsletter will be written in a style that is accessible to multiple audiences in terms of style and technical complexity (e.g. based on the Flesch scale). It will be made available via the website (and advertised via social media) as well as to those who have signed up from the website. It will be shared directly with sister projects and networks (e.g. see Table 2) as well as other important organisations as defined by the Clustering Plan (Deliverable 8.5). The project will benefit substantially, in terms of reach, from its partners that are well-connected with the seafood and aquaculture industries such as ABT, Eurofish, and EAS.

3.4.2 Trade Publications

At least four trade publications will be created, i.e. at least one within each project year. The project will use Eurofish Magazine as its primary vehicle to communicate project news and results. Eurofish Magazine (produced by project partner Eurofish) is a bimonthly and freely available online publication that is accessed by a considerable network of relevant stakeholders. Eurofish has 13 member countries spread across Europe and is also part of the FISH INFOnetwork for fish marketing and information services. The network was created in late 1970's by the FAO (Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations) (see Figure 8). It was created to assist the fishery sector particularly in developing countries and countries in transition. The network provides services to private industry and to governments. It is also widely known for its range of publications and periodicals as well as for the organisation of international conferences, workshops and training seminars.

Figure 8: Eurofish INFOnetwork (image courtesy of Eurofish)

However, in addition to Eurofish Magazine, the project will explore additional options for trade publications such as the EU's Horizon Magazine and also EuroFIR e-news. EuroFIR (Euro-Food Information Resources) is a project partner who specifically creates media to support education and knowledge transfer to stakeholders within the food industry, including seafood and aquaculture.

3.4.3 Informational Videos

A suite of informational videos will be prepared by WRG Europe and other relevant project partners. These will be available on the project website and YouTube channel and shared via social media. Videos will target different audiences as follows:

Video Type	Audience(s)
Infographic style videos describing the project aims and objectives	For general audiences, both technical and non-technical
Specific technical videos describing project innovations (e.g. sensors or genomic tools)	Academic, industrial (SME and large industry), standards bodies, and policymakers
Filming at the Living Labs	Depending on content, this will target the general public (e.g. for consumer engagement/behaviours to support awareness of aquaculture) or industry (e.g. demonstration of specific project innovations)
Documentary-style films or motion graphics on the challenges of fishing, seafood supply and consumption	For general audiences of all types

Table 4: Target audiences for video media

3.4.4 Project Poster, Flyer, and Roll-Up

To promote the FishEUTrust project at conferences, exhibitions (e.g. Aquaculture Europe) and events (e.g. Open Days or hackathons), a project poster, roll-up, and flyer will be created within the first year. These will be distributed electronically but will be available to the consortium for printing and distribution at events. These media will be reviewed, updated and tailored depending on the event. For example, events involving school children will use media that uses appropriate language and imagery.

3.4.5 Educational Material

Specific educational materials will be created to inform students of all ages regarding the innovations of the project as well as more general material in regard to consumption of seafood,

challenges within the “Blue Economy”, and creating sustainability therein. This will take the form of digital media available on the website (articles and videos) as well as, potentially, the use of the Jove platform, which is a comprehensive repository of scientific scholarly and educational information.

3.5 Communication specific to the food/seafood trade

While publications in trade magazines such as Eurofish Magazine will have broad reach across the industry, the following specific organisations have been identified as critical pathways for communication. They provide a crucial link to industrial stakeholders whose adoption of the project innovations will enable assurances of seafood quality, safety, traceability, and authenticity. This could also include development of new standards and/or quality procedures, processes, and policy. Thus focused communication towards these groups is extremely important to the project. Communications could include directed emails informing recipients of key project results (e.g. validation of sensors), summary flyers of the project status, invites to events and open days, targeted sharing of social media posts, etc.

The list below includes alliances and associations of small scale fishing fleets as well as large scale fish production companies, and the list will be regularly reviewed and updated as the project progresses.

The European Fisheries Alliance is a coalition of European fishing fleets representing the interests of fishing fleets in the Member States of the European Union (18,000 fishermen and 3,500 vessels). <https://fisheriesalliance.eu>

Europêche is the representative body for fishermen in the EU representing around 45,000 vessels, both artisanal and large scale, 80,000 fishermen and counting 16 member organisations from 10 countries. <http://europeche.chil.me>

European Association of Fish Producers Organisations (EAPO) represents 28 POs from 9 EU Member States, with approximately 10,000 vessels, 3.5 million tonnes of landings and € 3 billion first sale value. <https://www.eapo.com>

AIPCE-CEP represents 19 EU National Associations from 12 Member States and 3 National Associations in Third countries (UK, Norway, Morocco), accounts for more than 3,900 enterprises and 128,000 persons (more than 80% representativeness at EU level). The value of the output of the industry represented by AIPCE-CEP amounts to around EUR 30 billion, about three and a half times the turnover of the EU catch sector. <https://www.aipce-cep.org>

European Fisheries Control Agency is a European Union agency that aims to promote the highest common standards for control, inspection and surveillance under the CFP. The EFCA will function at the highest level of excellence and transparency with a view to developing the necessary confidence and cooperation of all parties involved and, in so doing, to ensure effectiveness and efficiency of its operations. <https://www.efca.europa.eu/en>

Aquatic Network is a website that helps aquaculture and aquaponics businesses and allied organizations connect with customers and supporters. <https://www.aquanet.com>. Some examples of organizations the project could connect with include:

1. Instituto Portugues Do Mare Da Atmosfera Ip IPMA Portugal
2. Fundacion AZTI – AZTI FUNDAZIOA AZTI-Tecnalia Spain
3. Universiteit Gent UGent Belgium
4. Istituto Superiore Di Sanita ISS Italy
5. Rijksinstituut Voor Volksgezondheid En Milieu RIVM Netherlands
6. Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior Deinvestigaciones Cientificas CSIC Spain
7. Iceta Instituto De Ciencias, Tecnologias E Agroambiente Da Universidade Do Porto ICETA Portugal
8. Danmarks Tekniske Universitet DTU Denmark

9. Eigen Vermogen Van Het Instituut Voor Landbouwen Visserijonderzoek ILVO Belgium
10. Cefas United Kingdom
11. Institut De Recerca I Tecnologia Agroalimentaries IRTA Spain
12. Institut Technique De Developpement Des Produits De La Mer IDMER France
13. Universitat Rovira I Virgili URV Spain
14. Centro Interdisciplinar De Investigacao Marinha E Ambiental CIIMAR Portugal
15. Aqua Tt Uetp Company Limited BY GUARANTEE AquaTT Ireland
16. Tarelaks AS Tarelaks Norway
17. MRAG Ltd MRAG United Kingdom
18. Rise Research Institutes Of Sweden AB RISE Sweden
19. Asociacion Nacional De Fabricantes De Conservas De Pescados Y Mariscoscentro Tecnico Nacional De Conservacion De Productos De La Pesca ANFACO Spain
20. Moreforskning Alesund AS MF Norway
21. Sparos LDA SPAROS Portugal
22. Spread European Safety Geie Spes Italy
23. Aeiforia SRL AEIFORIA Italy
24. Zachodniopomorski Uniwersytet Technologiczny W Szczecinie ZUT Poland
25. Campden BRI Magyarorszag Nonprofit Korlatolt Felelossegu Tarsasag CBHU Hungary
26. The Queen's University Of Belfast QUB United Kingdom
27. European Consumers Union ECU Italy
28. AQUIMER France
29. XENOBICS Ltd XEN United Kingdom
30. Inskie Centrum Rybactwa Spolka Zoo ICR Poland
31. Westcounty Mussels Of Fowey LTD WCM United Kingdom
32. PTC Phage Technology Center GMBH PTC Germany
33. SKALOMA AE SKALOMA Greece
34. Predell Services PS France
35. Biorex Food Diagnostics Limited BFD United Kingdom

3.6 Events (Communication and Dissemination)

Events are a very important means to engage face-to-face with the general public, industry, and policymakers to communicate key project aims and innovations. This is particularly important for consumer engagement to discuss and receive feedback about products from aquaculture, buying preferences, and general perceptions on the industry and seafood. A series of events are planned through the life of the project and will include:

Events for General Communication:

- Open days at each Living Lab: These will be targeted primarily towards consumer engagement. These open days are designed to provide the general public with information about aquaculture and to educate consumers about the importance of innovative seafood practices. It will also be an opportunity to discuss with consumers about their seafood purchasing preferences and how aquaculture and FishEU Trust can support this. This will also include tasting events at gourmet evenings, initially targeted at the Bugenvilla CLL in Croatia. The geographical spread of the Living Labs across Europe will enable a wide section of public to access the Living Labs.
- School Hackathons: In order to educate children about seafood consumption, aquaculture, and sustainable fishing, the CLLs will also arrange hackathons for children of school age.
- Seminars and workshops for older students: Events such as AquaNor will be arranged to discuss and present the latest developments and innovations in seafood and aquaculture. This is with a view to engaging pre-university, undergraduate, or post-graduate students to sustain and grow interest in related academic and industrial fields.

Events for Dissemination:

- Technical Open days at each Living Lab: These are targeted at specific end-users who are interested in the project innovations, such as the sensors or genomic techniques to understand how these can support their own needs. These events will also be open to policy and standards bodies, including the European Commission. The geographical spread of the Living Labs across Europe will enable a wide section of public to access the Living Labs.
- Workshop events for knowledge exchange between FishEUTrust and related projects to promote key results, best practices, shared learning, and standards.

4. Dissemination

Dissemination of FishEUTrust results is vital for the project to achieve lasting impact. Going beyond engaging target audiences and communicating project objectives and methods, FishEUTrust's dissemination measures will raise awareness of project outputs and innovations. These activities will highlight the importance of the FishEUTrust concepts and technologies and show how outputs can be adopted and exploited beyond the project funding period. FishEUTrust dissemination is tailored to create awareness of the project within key industrial stakeholders, business developers (e.g. via WP3), standards and policy bodies, and business-to-business organisations (e.g. retail), in addition to academics and research organisations (e.g. to create further research opportunities and projects within Horizon Europe). Public engagement will continue with the aim of building trust among consumers whilst supporting healthy choices and lifestyles through FishEUTrust innovations and concepts.

4.1 Internal and external dissemination

There are two strands to FishEUTrust dissemination: internal and external. Internal activities will consist primarily of creating awareness of exploitable results within the consortium by effective management. The project structure (Figure 1) has an Innovation and Exploitation Board whose role is to seek pathways to exploitation of results including commercialisation. At project meetings, there will be a re-occurring agenda item to discuss key exploitable results and how they can be advanced, including any necessary intellectual property protection. Regular management communications will also announce important achievements to the consortium and all documents will be available on the project NextCloud shared drive.

External dissemination activities will engage those outside the project around key exploitable results, and includes user communities in academia and industry, and other stakeholders such as consumers and the public, policymakers, and government agencies. External dissemination will take four main forms: 1) Attendance at exhibitions at relevant conferences and trade events, 2) Open days, workshops and events at the CLLs, 3) Targeted communications (email, social media, etc.) to key stakeholders (e.g. as identified by clustering plans) of significant project results, and 4) Publishing papers in relevant peer-reviewed scientific and trade journals. Additional measures will include, where applicable, policy briefs written for government agencies, regional authorities, and other public bodies, and advice notes produced for companies.

All dissemination activities will be supplemented by targeted media campaigns aimed at informing as wide an audience as possible about FishEUTrust and project outputs including technology developments. Project updates and news on non-sensitive results (IP) will be submitted to general and trade magazines (see also Section 3.5) and visual and audio media outlets. Condensed updates will be shared on social media and the FishEUTrust website (in the form of news items and articles).

4.2 Conference attendance and exhibitions

Conference attendance and exhibition at conferences (e.g. in trade halls) is an important dissemination mechanism. Through its experienced and well-connected consortium, the project will identify key conferences and/or sector-specific trade shows as part of ongoing CD&E activity where important outputs can be presented. Conferences will be selected on appropriateness of

themes and opportunities for the consortium to disseminate information to the most relevant audiences. As the list below indicates, some of these events will be more focused on dissemination towards academic audiences and others also include ambitions towards industrial uptake. Examples include:

- **IEEE BigData conference and the Applied Machine**, the academic conference is a leading forum for disseminating knowledge on Big Data research and applications
- **EuroSensors**, which is the leading European academic conference devoted to advancing high tech in sensors, actuators, microsystems and nanosystems.
- **IEEE Sensors Conference** this conference provides access to a well established forum of research scientists, engineers and practitioners from academia and industry working on sensors technology
- **EFFoST International Conference**, this conference has been selected as it focuses on promoting interdisciplinary and intersectoral collaborations within the food sector, thus its attendance should comprise academics, industry, and policymakers
- **The Global Seafood Marketplace 25-27/04/2023** Barcelona ES, the world's largest seafood trade event with attendees from across the world comprising buyers, suppliers, media and other industry professionals
- **Aquaculture Europe 2023** September 18-21, 2023 – Vienna AT, one of the largest aquaculture trade shows in the world
- **Aqua24, Copenhagen, DE**, 26-29 August 2024, this is a premium event for all organisations and projects involved in seafood and aquaculture

This list will be updated throughout the project. Creating awareness of key conferences is a critical internal communication requirement (i.e. partners being informed of upcoming conferences or declaring their intention to attend/present). To ensure this occurs efficiently, a spreadsheet will be created on the shared project server where partners can input this information.

4.3 Publishing papers

It is envisaged that around 20 peer-reviewed papers (i.e. about one per technical beneficiary) will be published in high-quality journals over the lifetime of FishEUTrust. Some journals will include:

- Nature Magazine
- International Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Studies
- Journal of Cleaner Production
- Journal of Agricultural and Marine Sciences
- Aquaculture International
- Journal of Aquaculture and Fisheries
- IEEE Internet of Things Journal
- IEEE Transactions on Big Data
- International Journal of Genomics
- Journal of Sensors
- International Journal of Sensors

The authors of peer-reviewed papers will acknowledge the FishEUTrust project and the financial support provided by the EU. Links to the FishEUTrust website will be provided on the website of the publishing journal for people to follow to learn more about the project overall. General publication guidelines will be based around those provided in Deliverable 9.5: "Project Management Guidelines". The spreadsheets on dissemination reporting, publications, communications, and publications/scientific papers will be available at the FishEUTrust Nextcloud share point. Siân Astley of EuroFIR will collect the publication and dissemination details for reporting.

4.3.1 Open access and data management

Where appropriate, papers will be published using the newly established European Commission's Open Access publishing platform: ORE (see via: <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>). This allows rapid, free, and open access publication, enabling others to build quickly upon new ideas, whilst maximising the impact and of research outcomes to the Commission, the scientific and industrial communities, and the general public.

All data generated by FishEUTrust will be centrally stored (for access and retrieval) on computers at JSI using the Institute's standard archiving data control procedures. Data will be backed up on to secure areas of a central server designated for this purpose. Moreover, where appropriate, data will also be stored on the Zenodo open repository maintained by CERN. Data storage will follow the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable) principles, which recognises the need to balance openness and protection of potentially commercially sensitive information. As such, all due consideration will be given to IPR, security, and privacy concerns associated with distributing project results prior to any external dissemination.

4.4 Networking, Clustering, and Co-Creation

Links with related projects, organisations, and networks will be essential to maximise dissemination (and communication) reach and impacts thereof. Clustering planning is a fundamental project output of FishEUTrust and is embodied within Deliverable 8.5. It has been mentioned that discussions are already underway with the Sea2See project, with other projects such as SAFE and EUMofa (relating to partner Eurofish) also as potential candidates. The shared networks and contacts of these project will enhance reach as well as preventing duplication of effort. Moreover, key conferences (such as Aquaculture Europe) will be targeted for co-hosting of stands and also co-presenting projects during paper sessions.

It has also been mentioned in Section 2.3 that the FishEUTrust consortium possesses many highly connected and networked partners, including EuroFish, EuroFIR, EAS, and Norce. These partners make the overall reach of the project substantial in order to disseminate key results.

5. Exploitation

The legacy of FishEUTrust will be a suite of tools integrating metagenomics, genetics and stable isotope approaches, smart control systems for safety and quality, digital technologies/solutions for traceability and engagement tools, and data platforms tested and validated in industrial and consumer settings. A comprehensive Exploitation Plan (D3.5) will be developed by Redinn (IT). To elaborate the exploitation strategy, specific exploitation and business plans will be developed to test and validate installations within the Living Labs. Subsequently, WP1 and WP3 will determine technical and economic performances once the appropriate technology readiness level is achieved. Similarly, these WPs will validate the technologies against standards and regulations to facilitate and support market uptake and implementation.

The depth and breadth of the consortium (covering a wider range of stakeholder groups), including highly networked partners, such as EuroFish, EuroFIR and EAS, will generate broad interest in the outcomes and create opportunities for future exploitation. Industrial potential is diverse from small, localised producers, to larger European and global industries. The multifaceted range of technology developments within FishEUTrust, supported by a world-leading consortium, are designed to respond to user communities' different needs. Key Performance Indicators will help measure interest and uptake in response to business development plans (e.g. number of enquiries made to the project, number of organisations registered to the project, etc.). The business plan will be developed and consolidated during the project (WP3) but it will focus creation on exploitation opportunities, which can be converted into commercial applications or non-commercial opportunities (e.g. academic exploitation).

More specifically:

Stage 1 (In Project): Initial stages of the business plan will focus on the dissemination and consumer/industrial engagement programmes, including site visits, to raise awareness and can be reinforced by examples at validation sites to stimulate commercial interest and opportunities.

Stage 2 (Immediate post project): The exploitation plan will focus on outcomes and how these can deliver significant benefits to both industrial and RTD partners. For RTD partners, sensors, tools and data platforms developed within FishEUTrust can readily be deployed and/or adapted to suit other applications particularly within the food sector, leading to future collaboration opportunities. SME partners, particularly MICRUX, BELIT, and DigitalSmart, should see growth in awareness, revenue, market share, and staff exemplified through the Living Labs. Tasks in WP3 will also ensure that funding and investment is stimulated post-project to sustain project outputs. For MICRUX, BELIT, and DigitalSmart, the key post-project (Stage 2) impact is recognition and awareness of their technologies and offerings, which can lead to exploitation and growth in Stage 3.

Stage 3 (Subsequent exploitation and commercialisation): Recognition and awareness by food production companies allied to investment opportunities will allow commercial growth alongside other exploitation routes. For example, MICRUX has estimated an increase of revenue regarding their sensors of 10% by 2027, 10% in staff growth within four years, two new service offerings within four years, and two new collaborative projects can arise from FishEUTrust activities. The project creates substantial potential to improve trends in European fish and seafood consumption and other related healthy food choices. KPIs will be monitored through government statistics, where appropriate. Moreover, the position of European Aquaculture Society (EAS), CETGA and Portuguese Aquaculture Association – APA, as central hubs amongst the numerous aquaculture associations and other agencies, will be a crucial element augmenting exploitation.

5.1 A consortium structured to enhance exploitation

The consortium is structured to maximise exploitation opportunities with the entire supply chain represented by at least one beneficiary. This will be augmented by the project Advisory Board, which will include commercial organisations interested in adopting project outcomes.

Figure 9: The diverse project consortium to support exploitation and impact

The breadth and depth of the FishEUTrust consortium (shown in Figure 9) underpins exploitation and commercial opportunities through creation of a “network of networks”, utilising beneficiaries’ existing networks. Moreover, for academic beneficiaries, FishEUTrust outputs will support formation of new research proposals and collaborative partnerships.

5.3 Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)

An essential part of exploitation is management of intellectual property. Successful exploitation, especially commercialisation of results, relies on IPR within the consortium being available and supporting the generation of new IP. The consortium will protect, share, manage, and exploit IP generated within FishEUTrust to maximise outreach, engagement, impact, and benefit.

IP related aspects of the FishEUTrust refer to:

1. Protection for sensor and labelling technology.
2. Development of a novel suite of tools integrating metagenomics, genetic and stable isotope approaches.
3. Innovative data platforms supporting technology integration, consumer engagement and data infrastructure.

IPR will be managed according to the best international standards and best practices and in accordance with the European Charter for Researchers. Traceability and recognition of Background and Foreground IP will be handled via the coordinator, the data management plan (DMP), and the innovation/exploitation manager. Scientific results of general interest will be disseminated through Open Access or subscription. However, authors wishing to publish work that includes foreground IP must obtain the necessary permissions from beneficiaries providing the foreground prior to publication; providers must not delay on create barriers to this dissemination unnecessarily. Procedures for IP protection and exploitation are defined in the Consortium Agreement and follow the DESCA agreement guidelines.

Dissemination of key exploitable knowledge will be restricted by the Consortium Agreement until protection is achieved through patents or other means (e.g., license such as Creative Commons). The management team will closely follow technological developments and will, for novelty outputs, facilitate IP protection as appropriate.

Each beneficiary will disclose promptly to others resulting IP during the term of the consortium agreement. Beneficiaries are expected to co-operate around the preparation and submission of patent applications and any other resulting IP applications. Each beneficiary will own IP generated under the project by their efforts and will be responsible for securing protection, as necessary.

5.4 Strengthening European innovation capacity

In accordance with the “Innovation Union” initiative’s goals for economic growth and job creation, FishEUTrust will create an EU-wide suite of novel tools and generate new knowledge as well as potentially also commercial products and services. These will facilitate continued leadership of the EU in providing world-class solutions and best practices to address food safety and strengthen authenticity and quality of fish and seafood for the benefit of European citizens. Industrial beneficiaries will assist in demonstrating key exploitable results, thereby potentially also increasing their economic value. Uptake of key exploitable results by SMEs will help to increase competitiveness in a global market through the development of schemes to protect product quality and origin. FishEUTrust’s results will also impact on environmental sustainability, food production, and public health. FishEUTrust key exploitable results will contribute to making the European seafood sector competitive and its products recognised and desired on a global scale.

6. Evaluation and Adjustment of Planned Activities

As stated above, this plan is a living document that will be updated regularly, based upon the effectiveness of dissemination, communication, and exploitation activities. Measures for monitoring and evaluating (KPIs) the effectiveness of activities including:

Engagement Type	Metric for Measuring Success	Target
Website	Click-through rate	> 5%
	Bounce rate	< 40%
	Number of monthly visitors	>100
Social media	Number of followers, Twitter	>300
	Number of followers, LinkedIn	>500
	Number of posts per platform	Min 12/year
	Number of clicks through to project website	10/month
Informational videos	Number released on to website and YouTube	Min 4
	Total number of YouTube views	5000
Website articles	Number of articles per year	Min 2
Newsletter	Number produced	2/year
	Number of signups to receive newsletter	10/year
	Number of times the newsletter is viewed/ downloaded from the website	50/year
Food trade communications	Number of articles published in print/online	12 articles within the project
Media engagement	Number of articles published in print/online by other media outlets (EC, Jove, etc.)	6 within the project
Public engagement talks	Number of public talks to target audiences	4 within the project
Events	Number of CLL open days/workshops held	5
	Number of PR events held	1
Published papers	Number of papers published in peer-reviewed journals	20
Conference attendance	Number of conferences/exhibitions attended by consortium members	2/year
	Number of papers and/or posters presented at conferences	2/year
Patents	Number of patents applied for as a result of FishEUTrust research results	3 within the project
Industrial engagement	Number of industrial (SMEs or large) companies confirming interest in FishEUTrust technologies/outputs	10 within the project

Table 5: FishEUTrust communication, dissemination, and exploitation metrics of success.

Strategies, activities, and these KPIs will be evaluated annually at project meetings as well as on an ongoing basis by the WP8 team. New or alternative measures – as well as changes to activities – will be proposed if it appears existing ones are not proving as effective or successful as hoped.

